

LIGHTWEIGHT DESIGN OF COMPOSITE BODY FOR ELECTRIC MICROBUS

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to propose a preliminary design methodology for electric bus structures by implementing the finite-element method via HyperWorks 2017. The bus structure is designed based on various criteria such as the strength of the bus structure under various driving conditions, bending and torsion stiffness requirements and the rollover test according to UN ECE R66. The objective function is to minimize the mass and the cost of the material for the microbus body having varied lamina thickness and stacking sequence. The mass-optimized model yields the structural weight of 1,677 kilograms yet having an identical constraint of the vertical displacement as the base model and costs 23,907 USD. The cost-optimized model, on the other hand, weighs 1,972 kilograms but the cost is greatly reduced to 16,488 USD.

DESIGN CRITERIA

Designed bus is different in type, and appropriate that reason inventing diverse layout. In the engineering analysis, the design criteria being created according 6 condition. The loads and constraints in finite element analysis are specified in this fashion bending stiffness, torsion stiffness, natural frequency of the body structure, longitudinal loading, lateral loading and quasi-static loading test.

Deflection under bending of the based model

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Bending stiffness

$$K_b = \frac{W}{d_{max}}$$

The longitudinal vertical centre plane of the vehicle

$$\alpha = 90^\circ - \arcsin\left(\frac{800}{H_c}\right)$$

Torsion stiffness

$$K_t = \frac{Ft}{\theta}$$

The minimum energy of quasi-static loading

$$E_T = 0.75Mg\Delta h$$

GENERAL MODEL INFORMATION

The bus a monocoque structure which having 24 passenger seats. The dimensions of the bus are 2.4 meters wide, 7.8 meters long, and 3.2 meters high. The bus model is decomposed 9 components. In this process, possibility is conducted by modifying the thickness of face and core of the designed components. Respective components are defined as conformable responses and constraints. Those are bending stiffness, torsion stiffness and natural frequency which the parameters of response are static displacement on the vertical axle, static displacement at the front wheel and frequency, respectively.

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MATERIALS OF BUS STRUCTURE

The sandwich structure consists of woven fabrics composite and foam core is adopted on most of the monocoque structure. ASTM D3410 for compressive properties and ASTM D3518 for in-plane shear properties.

Material properties	G400	G600	C200	HP100
Longitudinal modulus, E_1 (MPa)	18,036	16,281	78,493	105
Transverse modulus, E_2 (MPa)	18,036	16,281	78,493	
In-plane shear modulus, G_{12} (MPa)	2,219	2,942	2,122	28
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.053	0.04	0.052	0.4
Longitudinal tensile strength, F_{1t} (MPa)	206.6	309	411.4	2.5
Longitudinal compressive strength, F_{1c} (MPa)	97.8	195	370.6	1.65
Transverse tensile strength, F_{2t} (MPa)	206.6	309	411.4	
Transverse compressive strength, F_{2c} (MPa)	97.8	195	370.6	
In-plane shear strength, S_{12} (MPa)	27.45	27.9	22.4	35
Mass density (kg/m ³)	1,588	1,717	1,336	100
Material cost per kilograms (USD)	5.5	3.8	111	18.8

SIZE OPTIMIZATION RESULTS

Ply thickness of optimization model under base model, mass model

Component	BASE MODEL									MASS MODEL									COST MODEL								
	ceiling	pillar	battery	bottom	beam	floor	vent	roof	sub-floor	ceiling	pillar	battery	bottom	beam	floor	vent	roof	sub-floor	ceiling	pillar	battery	bottom	beam	floor	vent	roof	sub-floor
Thickness (mm)	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	16	48	65	64	63	61	56	55	54	4.8	23	63	35	69	64	34	47	18	5.6	12
Cost (1,000 USD)	1.36	1.46	10.0	5.40	0.42	6.24	1.50	2.39	0.94	1.48	1.54	10.8	5.07	0.33	2.22	1.00	0.75	0.65	1.24	1.04	5.07	5.20	0.29	1.91	0.56	0.82	0.37
Mass (kg)	198	213	213	787	62	459	219	521	11	195	200	179	604	27	193	84	154	31	171	192	277	748	53	242	103	184	12

Summary of parameter condition of bus model

	Stiffness		Frequency		Raw material cost	Total mass
	Bending	Torsion	Bending	Torsion		
Based model	34,600	106,000	14.3	17.9	29,708	2,682
Mass model	36,706	124,000	16.4	18.3	23,907	1,667
Cost model	37,268	114,814	14.5	18.6	16,488	1,972
Unit	N/mm	mm/degree	Hz	Hz	USD	kg

CONCLUSIONS

- The design and optimization of sandwich structure consisting of glass and carbon fiber/epoxy face and foam core for electric microbus. The sandwich structure is designed based on six constraints which are bending stiffness, torsion stiffness, natural frequency, two normal driving loading criteria, and rollover test.
- Nine components of bus structure are optimized based on minimizing mass and cost. The optimized structure shows improved performance and is lighter or cheaper. Two optimized models, mass-optimized and cost-optimized, are compared with the base model.